

Manufacturing with Fiber Metal Laminates

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Abstract

Fiber Metal Laminates (FML) are a family of hybrid materials, consisting of alternating layers of thin metal sheets and fiber reinforced polymer layers. The Fiber metal laminates were developed to obtain a metallic material with excellent fatigue resistance. Besides its fatigue resistance, the FML offer good damage tolerance properties in general, including impact resistance, fire resistance and corrosion resistance.

The members of the FML family may have different metal alloys, types of fibers and or polymers, lay-ups, fiber-orientations, etc., however, the basic concept is the same.

The material properties of FML can be related to the two main constituents: the metal alloys and the composite materials. The metal layers give the FML some ductility and plasticity, the composite layer allow the designer to tailor the laminate to its needs. Besides, the laminates are also layered materials, which has its impact on the number of failure modes for these laminates: not only metal and Fiber failure but also delaminations and buckling of thin layers.

The features of the constituents also have impact on the manufacturing processes and give the laminates a dual character: typical metal characteristics like the capability of plastic deformation, springback and good machining properties on one hand, and lay-up methodologies for large panels, like composite materials, on the other hand.

The plasticity of the laminates is employed in several manufacturing processes for FML. Simple forming operations like bending and stretching can be performed using flat laminates (semi finished parts). Complex double curved parts cannot be made of flat laminates; the limited failure strain of the fibers will prevent that. The plastic forming capability is dependent on the fiber orientations in the laminate and its lay-up. Thick laminates cannot be bent due to a limited interlaminar shear.

In addition to plastic deformation, the laminates can also be manufactured like composite materials: large integrated skin panels can be made in one or two lay-up and autoclave cycles. The big advantages here are the possibility of product integration (integration of local reinforcements) and the elimination of joints, due to the increased size of the panels.

When structural elements have to be attached to the skin or when the large panels have to be assembled in the final structure, joining techniques are required. Both riveting and bolting techniques can be applied, similar to the techniques used in conventional (metal) structures. To prepare these elements for assembly, by trimming edges and drilling holes, different machining processes can be used. The application of these processes is much alike the machining of metal alloys; the differences are related to the abrasive nature of the fibers and the susceptibility to delamination in case of large out-of-plane forces.

In this contribution a brief overview will be given about the different issues related to the manufacturing of FML as outlined above.

1. Introduction

Fiber Metal Laminates (FMLs) are based on a simple material concept: alternating layers of metal alloy and layers of fiber reinforced polymers (see figure 1). With respect to conventional metal alloys this concept offers very good Damage Tolerance properties in general and excellent fatigue resistance in particular.

Research in the past, starting with the aim to develop FMLs as a fatigue resistant materials, resulted in a thickness for the metal layers of about 0.3-0.5 mm and about 2-4 times 0.125 mm for the intermediate composite layers. The thickness of each layer and the number of layers depend on the particular FML-type.

Figure 1. Typical composition of a Fiber Metal Laminate

GLARE is the most well-known FML, made of layers of aluminum alloys and glass-fiber reinforced epoxies. Several GLARE-grades have been developed (see Table 1):

- unidirectional laminates and several types cross ply laminates;
- grades based on Al-2024 alloys and Al-7475 alloys;
- laminates with different lay-ups, ranging from a 2/1 lay-up (2 metal and 1 composite layer) to laminates with a large number of layers.

Table 1. Composition and constituents of some GLARE-grades

grade	Al. alloy	thickness [mm]	orientation	thickness [mm]
GLARE 1	7475-T761	0.3-0.4	Unidirectional	0.25
GLARE 2	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	Unidirectional	0.25
GLARE 3	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	Cross-ply (50-50)	0.25
GLARE 4	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	Cross-ply (67-33)	0.375
GLARE 5	2024-T3	0.2-0.5	Cross-ply (50-50)	0.5

Each type of laminate has its particular properties; some properties can be easily determined using the Rule of Mixture like for composites. Since the FMLs are a mixture of composites and metal alloys, the properties of the Fiber Metal Laminates reflect the characteristic behaviour of the two constituents. Fatigue resistance, anisotropy, lay-up technology are properties related to the composite constituent; plasticity, impact resistance and acceptable workshop properties are features related to the metal constituent.

In the following sections some characteristics of FML with respect to the manufacture of parts and structures are discussed. In the next section a brief overview is presented of the mechanical properties of FMLs. These properties can explain the limited formability of the laminates as discussed in the section about plastic forming. Since the plasticity is limited, only simple product shapes can be made from a flat laminate. In case of skin panels, smooth single or double curved shells, lay-up techniques are used. Even the local reinforcements like doublers are made in lay-up processes, often within the same process cycle. The lay-up

technique is described in the section 4. In section 5 some machining and joining techniques are discussed that can be applied to FML.

Finally, in sections 6 and 7, some concluding remarks are made and some references are given for further reading respectively.

2. Mechanical Properties

Due to its composition a Fiber Metal Laminate is an anisotropic material, and therefore, the laminate properties depend on the Fiber direction(s). An overview of selected mechanical properties of some GLARE laminates and some Aluminum alloys is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Some mechanical properties of some GLARE-grades and some aluminum alloys*

		GLARE-1	GLARE-2	GLARE-3	Al-2024	Al-7075
metal constituent		7475-T761	2024-T3	2024-T3	2024-T3	7075-T6
fiber orientation		UD	UD	CP	--	--
max. strength (<i>tensile</i>)[MPa]	L	1300	1230	755	440	538
	LT	360	320	755	435	538
yield strength (<i>tensile</i>)[MPa]	L	550	400	320	324	483
	LT	340	230	320	290	469
E-modulus [GPa]	L	64.7	65.6	57.5	72.4	71.1
	LT	49.2	50.2	57.5	72.4	71.1
max. strain [%]	L	4.6	5.1	5.1	13.6	8
	LT	7.7	13.6	5.1	13.6	8
Density [g/cm ³]		2.52	2.52	2.52	2.78	2.78

When compared to aluminum alloys the following features of GLARE can be observed:

- The tensile strength of the material in fiber direction (L), the primary loading direction, is much higher than the maximum strength of the aluminum alloys 2024 and 7075. Perpendicular to the fiber direction (LT), in case of an UD-laminate, the tensile strength is less.
- The yield strength is also higher in fiber direction for the UD-laminates, but the differences with monolithic materials are not as high as for the tensile strength. In LT-direction the yield strength has a lower value than for the aluminum alloys.
- Overall, the E- or Young's modulus for laminates is smaller than for metal alloys.
- The maximum or failure strain of the laminates in L-direction is limited by the failure strain of the fibers. In GLARE the glass fibers (S-glass) have a maximum strain of 4-5%, which is represented in the failure strain of the laminates. For UD-laminates the strain in LT-direction is dominated by the failure strain of the metal alloy.
- The density of GLARE-laminates is about 10% less when compared to aluminum alloys. When the fiber volume is increased, e.g. as in the GLARE-5 grade, a larger reduction of the density is possible (up to about 20%).

The most striking properties of GLARE are the damage tolerance properties. The crack growth rate can be reduced by a factor of 10 to 100, dependent on the laminate and its composition. But not only the fatigue resistance is improved significantly, also the impact resistance, the flame retardation, and the corrosion resistance are properties which are much better than for monolithic materials like aluminum alloys.

Application of GLARE laminates may result in weight savings of 10-30%, due to its excellent fatigue resistant behaviour. Therefore, higher allowables for fatigue loading are permitted and the load levels for GLARE can be increased significantly. Typical aircraft structures, dominated by fatigue, are for example the fuselage structures.

Just like metal alloys, Fiber Metal Laminates fail when the maximum values of stress or strain are exceeded. However, metal alloys have only one real failure mode: rupture or fracture due to the tensile stresses in (a part of) the cross section. Buckling or wrinkling is a failure that occurs at component or structural level.

FMLs have more than one failure mode, failure modes that are related to the constituents of the laminate and failures related to the structure or lay-up of the laminate.

Typical constituent failures are:

- Fiber failure, immediately followed by failure of the whole specimen or component. Fibers usually have a very small failure strain: glass fibers as used in GLARE, have a failure strain of 4-5%, but laminates based on fibers like aramid fibers have smaller limit strains. Fibers are elastic until failure, so at failure, the energy release is significant and causes considerable (local) damage to the laminate.
- Cracking of the matrix, when the failure limit of the matrix is exceeded. In many cases, especially when the large strain of the matrix is a local strain, this failure does not result in a failure of the specimen or product.
- Cracking or rupture of the metal layer. This failure mode is also common for monolithic metal sheets. This failure occurs only during bending or when the laminate is strained perpendicular to the fibers.

In addition to these constituent failures there are also consistency failures, failures by which the (local) coherence of the laminate is lost. In these failure modes the laminate delaminates or debonds. The cause for the delamination is the exceedance of the shear stress or the peel stress of the polymer or the metal/composite interface. The debonding may occur at several locations, like the primer layer, the resin rich layer, and the matrix/fiber interface, although some of the possible delamination locations can be excluded by the proper fabrication of the laminates.

3. Plastic Forming of Fiber Metal Laminates

Since about 60% (vol-percentage) of the laminate consists of metal the laminate can be deformed plastically just like sheet metal. However, the forming limits of FMLs are not as large as for the metal alloys.

In many forming operations, the fibers are the limiting factor in the deformation. This is also obvious from the failure strain of the GLARE-grades in Table 2. For UD-laminates in L-direction the failure strain of the laminate is low, about 4-5% in LT-direction, representing the failure strain of the glass fibers. The strain perpendicular to the fibers is larger, about 8-13%.

2-dimensional shapes

The plastic deformation capability of the laminates is applied in bending processes for the bending of profiles or stringers (see figure 2 for a few examples). For a 2/1 lay-up it does not matter whether the bend line is parallel or perpendicular to the fiber direction. In both cases the fibers are close to the neutral line and the fibers are hardly strained.

For thick lay-ups (4/3 lay-up and larger) the fiber direction becomes very important (see figure 3). When bending with the bend line parallel to the fiber direction, the minimum bend radius increases gradually, just like for aluminum alloys, where the minimum bend radius increases proportionally with increasing sheet thickness, more or less with a constant ratio of $(r/t)_{\min}$. When the bend line is perpendicular to the fiber direction than the minimum bend radius increases exponentially, and for lay-ups larger than a 4/3-lay-up a reasonable radius is not possible.

Figure 2. Profiles made by bending.

During bending of UD laminates with the bend line parallel to the fibers, the laminate fails first by cracking of the outer aluminum layer. When the lay-up is increased further, the interlaminar shear strength increases too and for large lay-ups (about 5/4- or 6/5-lay-up, dependent on layer thickness) delamination becomes the dominant failure mode.

direction on minimum bend radius

Figure 3 Influence of fiber

A phenomenon associated to plastic deformation is the spring back of the material. When a laminate is bent over a straight bend line, parallel with the fibers, the magnitude of the spring back is of the same order of magnitude as the spring back of aluminum alloys. However, when the laminate is bent with a bend line perpendicular to the fibers (except for the 2/1-lay-up) the fibers are strained too and increase the spring back considerably. Spring back angles as large as 20-40% of the applied bend angle can be measured.

3-dimensional shapes

The manufacture of double curved parts made of FMLs by pure metal forming processes is difficult. As stated before, the failure strain in fiber direction is small, which limits the complexity of the parts. In stretch forming operations, a typical process in the aircraft industry

for the manufacture of smooth double curved shells, only very shallow double curvatures are possible. The best method is to stretch form the (CP) laminate in bias direction ($\pm 45^{\circ}$) with the fiber directions. In that case a failure strain of more than 6% is possible.

Typical deep drawing or press forming operations involving combinations of tensile and compressive stresses cannot be applied to FMLs. The thin metal layers are too sensitive for buckling when a considerable compressive stress is applied to the laminate.

Another difficulty that reduces the applicability of forming processes for 3D-products is the spring back. In bending operations for stringers strains in the fibers are absent, thus resulting in a small to moderate spring back (comparable to the metal alloy). But, in 3D parts the fibers have to be strained anyhow. This will also result in considerable spring back. For stretch forming operations, already limited to shallow double curved shells, the spring back of the laminates causes a complicated calculation of the contour of the stretch form block.

The only 3D-shapes that can be deformed rather easily are so-called stiffening beads in flat skin panels or web plates. These beads are made by a rubber forming technique and only tensile strains are applied to the laminate.

4. Lay-up of large skin panels

Important applications for Fiber Metal Laminates are skin panels for the fuselage. Since FMLs like GLARE have excellent damage tolerance properties, these laminates are ideal for the manufacture of fuselage skins, local reinforcements like doublers, and stringers.

Other elements of the fuselage structure like fuselage frames, or other double curved parts, cannot be manufactured from FMLs. The main reason is that these parts require in-plane deformations, and the small failure strain limits the applicable deformations to very shallow or smooth curvatures. Besides, the spring back and the fiber orientation will cause difficulties too: frames having stretch and shrink flanges will have a gradually changing fiber orientation along the flanges, which is not desirable, and will have gradual changing spring back angles too. Finally, typical shrink flanges will tend to buckle due to the compressive loads on those flanges.

Manufacture of the skin and doublers

The skin and its doublers are made of an FML (e.g. GLARE) by a laminating process like the processes as used for composite structures. The layers of the skin are placed one after the other in a mould with the right curvature (see figure 4). The mould can be a single curved one or a double curved mould with smooth curvatures.

Figure 4. Lay-up of a wide, single curved fuselage skin.

A very important feature in this lay-up process is the application of the so-called "splices". The splicing concept enables the manufacturer of skin laminates to make much wider skins than the maximum width of the sheet metal constituent (see figure 5). The length of these skins is only limited by the pre-treatment equipment, since the sheets are retrieved from coil.

Figure 5. The splice concept (overlap splice).

Based on the splice idea, several configurations have been developed: butt splices and overlap splices, as presented in figure 5. All these splices have in common, that a gap or split between two adjacent metal sheets is restricted to one layer of the cross section. A gap or split in a subsequent layer is shifted. Laminating a skin using this concept result in a limited or no reduction of the mechanical properties of the laminate, dependent on the type of splice and the number of layers on the laminate.

Using the splice concept, the size of the panel is limited only by the manufacturing equipment: the pre-treatment facilities and the autoclave used for the curing of the laminates. This results in large panels (see figure 6), which reduces the number of joints in a fuselage significantly.

During the lay-up process not only the skins can be placed in the mould, also doublers and other reinforcing layers can be laminated at the same time as the skin laminate. In those cases, the curing process for skin and the doublers are performed in the same autoclave cycle.

Figure 6. Large 2D skin panel (about 12 x 3.5 m)

Manufacture of 3D parts and thick stringers

Using the formability of the metal layers or thin laminates together with the lay-up process, interesting new products can be developed.

The thin metal sheets can be deformed in 3-dimensional shapes that after proper pre-treatment are assembled in 3-dimensional FML-parts, parts that cannot be manufactured from a laminate.

A similar sequence is used for the manufacture of thick stringers. In this case thin laminates are formed in thin profiles or stringers, and subsequently assembled into thick stringers.

Applying this sequence, which is only applicable due to the specific features of the FML concept and its constituents (plasticity, layered composition), parts are manufactured like stringer couplings (see figure 7) that have very small bend radii. These stringer couplings fit into a very tight and narrow space left by the stringers.

Figure 7 *Stringer couplings, made by assembly (bonding) of pre-deformed GLARE laminates (left and right) and the original one of machined aluminum (centre).*

The manufacture of these stringer couplings serve as example for the combination of the typical production processes which are used for metal alloys or composites, a combination that results in new parts and processes. Parts that have properties that cannot be achieved by one of the constituents alone, but obtained only by a combination of these materials and/or the manufacturing processes, like the stringer coupling.

Another typical example in the case of GLARE is the combination of an excellent fatigue resistance and the easy visibility of e.g. impact damages.

5. Machining and Joining of FML

Before the parts are assembled in (sub)structures, the parts have to be machined to their final dimensions and prepared for the subsequent joining process. In this paragraph a few comments will be made with regard to the machining and joining processes.

Machining

A large variety of different machining processes can be applied to Fiber Metal Laminates. The main features of the FML, important for the machining processes, are the fiber system and the layered structure of the laminates.

In GLARE e.g., the used fibers are glass fibers. The fibers have a large impact on the machineability of GLARE. The glass fibers are hard and abrasive and will increase the wear of cutting tools. This problem is overcome by the use of special carbide materials for the cutting tools. So with respect to machining of metal alloys, the geometry of the cutting tools can be unchanged, the most important difference should be the applied material for the cutting tool. The same is true when the fibers in the FML are carbon fibers or aramid fibers. Carbon fibers also cause considerable wear of the cutting tools, aramid fibers require a constantly

sharp tooling for proper cutting of these fibers. The slightest deterioration of the sharpness causes “hairy” cutting edges.

The second important feature is the lay-up of the material. The layered structure of the material will have an impact on the cutting forces, in particular to the forces perpendicular to the laminate. When e.g. the feed force during drilling becomes too large, delamination at the lower surface of the laminate occurs. Dull tools increase this problem when the feed force is increased to obtain the same cycle time. Proper control of these forces during drilling is required. For edge milling operations the helix angle of the drill bit should be small, otherwise delamination at the top surface occurs.

Figure 8. Front views (left) and cross section (right) of milled GLARE laminates

For drilling and milling processes, when special carbide tools are used, the results are excellent (see figure 8). In addition, also new cutting technologies like water jet cutting are applicable to GLARE laminates.

Joining

For the assembly of structures separate parts have to be joined. Typical joining techniques for metal alloys are bolting, riveting, bonding and welding, and for composite parts bolting and bonding. The joining techniques for FMLs are similar as for metal alloys, except that the laminates cannot be welded.

For pin-loaded joints like bolted and riveted joints, the same procedures can be used as for metallic structures, and often the same fasteners are applicable. The installation of the fasteners, the applied sealants, etc., all can be the same as for conventional structures. The only difference is the limited hole expansion that is allowed when the rivets or bolts are installed. For example the squeeze force in conventional riveting causes a small hole expansion due to the radial pressure acting from the shaft of the rivet on the edge of the hole. For metal alloys this expansion introduces beneficial compressive stresses in tangential direction of the hole, which postpones crack initiation from that hole. In FMLs this hole expansion should be minimized, since the pressure applied on the edge of the hole may delaminate the FML.

Adhesive bonding is a natural joining principle for the Fiber Metal Laminates. Each metal layer is pre-treated before lamination, by degreasing, pickling, anodizing, and application of a primer layer. When different structural elements are joined, these parts could be joined by adhesive bonding, which is applied in a second autoclave cycle. Prior to this bonding process, the surfaces should be cleaned.

6. Concluding remarks

In this paper some issues with respect to the manufacturing of FML-parts are discussed. The discussion can be summarized in a few lines, representing the most important differences when compared to metal alloys or full composites:

- FMLs exhibit several properties that are directly related to its constituents, like plasticity and ductility (metal), and anisotropy and a layered structure (composites)
- FMLs have multiple failure modes: failure of the constituents or failure of the coherence between the layers i.e. delamination.
- The formability of FMLs is poor and the spring back is considerable. Therefore, the application of forming processes to FMLs is limited.
- Large shells, including (local) reinforcements, made of FMLs for skin structures are made by lay-up technology, which resembles composite manufacturing. In this process splicing technology is very important.
- Machining and joining processes are much alike the processes as used for fabrication of metal structures. The most important differences are related to tool wear and possibility for delaminations.

7. References

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